

Students Perception on Effective Students Participatory Systems in Institutional Governance

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Abstract:- Students participation in institutions of higher learning has been associated with positive student's outcomes such as increased levels of satisfaction, positive civic development, active positive public life and prosocial behaviour. However, the colonial educational management system comes with a type of student participation that only looks at formal representative structures such as student's unions or guild executives and formal institutional governance structures where one or two students are elected to represent their colleagues in form of sitting on some university governance structures. The majority of students populous strongly feel this kind of colonial student's governance system does not adequately provide a true reflection of student's participation in the management of modern education systems hence the continuation of antisocial conduct that tend to disrupt the peaceful learning environment in terms of class boycotts, demonstrations and riots. Eventually, this leads to a compromised quality of education systems. The purpose of the study therefore was to explore what constituted student's participation using student's lenses. The significance of the study was that it established the existing gaps in the current participatory structures and proposed a suitable students participatory model that offers solutions to the problem of participation. The study used a qualitative methodological design within an explorative perspective view. Data was collected using semi-structured questionnaires and focused group discussions, reviews of literature and observations. Thematic analysis was used to analyse data and the results were presented using thematic designs. The study established that there existed a wide gap between the majority students and the union leadership and also between management and the student's majority groupings. A decentralised model of student's participatory system was proposed that would offer more informal and formal structures to increased student's participation in decision making process.

Keywords:- Student Participation, Decisions Making, Antisocial Behaviour, Higher Education, Decolonisation, Education System, Students Representations, Decentralisation's.

I. INTRODUCTION

Higher education institutions (HEIs) are critical and essential actors in the promotion of societal development and lifelong learning (Block 2016). They have been known to have a rich endowments of knowledge and a unique capacity to develop skills and foster critical developmental knowledge. Further, they possess the potential to mobilize educational resources and provide learning opportunities for diverse populations in society (Bieler & McKenzie 2017). Through teaching, research and consultancy services the institutions of higher learning play pivotal roles in actualization of viable solutions to key problems facing society today.

Students are a critical component of the successful institutions of higher learning though less appreciated in reality. In fact, the institutions of higher learning cannot exist without the presence of students. The higher the populations of the students and with diversity background, the more the likelihood that the institution is expected to prosper (Weller 2003).

Since students are a key stakeholders of a successful institutions of higher learning management is required to ensure that students are part of the decision making process. This is because most of the decisions that are made in the institutions of higher learning both directly and indirectly affect the students who are always the majority in term of the numbers (Aikens et al 2016). It is very imperative to indicate that students' participation in institutional decision making process comes with high positive returns both on the students themselves as well on the management side.

To begin with, Students participation in institutions of higher learning has been associated with positive student's outcomes such as increased levels of satisfaction, positive civic development, positive sense of responsibility, active positive public life, willingness to volunteer and prosocial behaviour, leadership training and personal responsibility values.

However, the colonial educational management system comes with a type of student participation that only looks at formal representative structures such as student's unions or guild executives and specific university governance structures such as the senate and the body of studies where one or two students are elected to represent their colleagues in form of sitting on some university governance structures

(Antal 2013). The majority of students populous however, strongly feel this kind of colonial system does not adequately provide solutions to the current scenario of modern education system hence the continuation of antisocial conducts that tend to disrupt the peaceful learning environment in terms of class boycotts, demonstrations and riots (Asherman 2016). Further, it is also observed that this system of student's representation does not reflect a true picture of full student's participation in any way one looks at it. The current system therefore sustains serious governance weaknesses that tend to compromise quality of the education systems. The main argument advanced being that there are limited levels of participatory structures offered by these formal systems in terms of numbers, levels of engagements, diversity of participation and also flexibility in term of the frequency of meetings and the room for equity and openness of the expected dialogue (Barth 2013). The majority of the students who are often left out of the process of involvements and participation have always asked questions as to why management has often left them out in fundamentals of decision making processes.

There is a wide gap that has been created between the majority of students and student's leadership and between the majority of students and management (Baker-Shelley 2017). It is always this wide separation sustained in the system where most of the conflicts between students and management have been generated. From the managerial formal point of view, it is assumed that students have always participated in decision making process. However, on the contrary the majority of the students have not been accorded an opportunity to participate in the decision-making process.

II. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

It has been observed that there exist several weaknesses in the participation of students in decision making process in institutions of higher learning in Zambia. From the management point of view, it is perceived that when students are represented in some formal university governance structures, then there is student's participation. On the other had however, student's participation using lenses of students is totally different from the management view perspectives. In reality therefore there is a gap between the majority student's movements and their leadership and between student's movements and management. There is very little empirical information that have focused on the what constitute student's participation using the student's perspectives. This study is so critical and it is required to create a new body of knowledge that supports and sustains majority student's participation in institutional decision-making process.

A. Research Objectives

- To explore students' perception on the student's guilds forms of participation in institutional governance
- To assess the student's levels of participation in institutional governance
- To find out what constitute participation using student's lenses

- To propose a suitable student's participatory model that improves the levels of student's participation in institutional governance structures
- To explore the benefits of student's participation

B. Purpose of Study

The purpose of the study will be to explore what constitute full student's participation using student's perceptions. Students representation is a complex field and also dynamic. What management regard as student's participation might have a completely different view from that of students both in the wider and narrow senses. Therefore, this study has explored what really constitute student's participation with maximum collaborations.

C. Significance of Study

This study will generate new body of knowledge that will be useful by policy makers, planners, administrators, educationist and regulatory authorities in planning and strategic realignment with respect to students' participation in decision making process. It is believed that through this study a new model of student's participation shall be put in place with both informal and informal structures that aim at soliciting maximum student's participation in decision making as well as in general activities of the higher institutions of learning. When the majority of students are able to participate in the management of the institution of higher learning, this will lead to more harmony and peace and positive social student's behavioural patterns both in the short and long term basis.

III. LITERATURE REVIEWS

A. Introductions

Institutions of higher learning are believed to be well positioned to synthesise viable solutions in solving societal problems both in the short and long term basis. Research however indicate that there is still a wide gap between the institutions of higher learning and the community (Beringer2006). It is further argued that for institutions of higher learning to provide comprehensive and effective decision, there is need to make effective collaboration with students who are key stakeholders in decision making at that levels (Bevington & Dixon 2005).

Students are a critical aspect of the institutions of higher learning. The success of every institution of higher learning partly lies with successful recruitment and maintenance of students in the whole lifelong of the university. Students play a vital role in shaping and influencing health and sound policy formulation, implementations and appraisal. However, research shows that there are less studies that have been conducted to deal with student's participatory force in the governance of institutions of higher learning (Bhasin 2003).

Further, studies (Bieler & McKenzie 2017) also show that students participations and representations in decision making has also been understudied for a long time now. This gap of lack of empirical studies in such a delicate and critical area also suggest that students have been

understimated when it comes to the reality of their importance in strategic decision making process in higher institutions of learning (Block 2016).

This study shall endeavour to highlight the critical role of student's participation in decision making process. Radical decision making process entails taking a modern approach to problem solving and breaking the ice. This concept looks at the reality of the fact that contrary to the primitive school of thought that distances students from all the institutional and corporate decision making process, it now a mandatory requirement that all students as much as possible be mobilized together towards mutual and conventional decision and participatory frameworks and mainstreaming dialogue, participation, inclusivity and collaborative efforts.

Murray (2018) conducted a study on institutions of higher learning to see the effectiveness of quality policy formulation to be made in partnership with students' efforts for solving societal problems. Using the systematic review of literature as the research methodological approach, it was found that student's initiative approach in sustainable higher education was understudied but there was such high evidence showing that there is growing appreciation of the understanding the critical roles that students play in improvement of society and higher learning institutions (Luescher-Mamashela 2013).

Further, this studies also revealed that students are working to increase the uptake of participation through multi-stakeholder collaborations, collective action and interdisciplinary (Lizzio & Wilson 2009). This review identifies a lack of engagement with intersectionality (interrelated environmental and social issues) and highlights the need to redirect future efforts research, calling for increased comparative research studies and research syntheses to provide greater depth to our understanding of student-led initiatives (Klemen 2014).

From this study it can be seen that student's efforts have always been hindered by lack of appreciations from management and often they have been kept at the distance from most of the activities happening at the centre of decision making in the institution of higher learning.

There are basically critical barriers that arise when students participatory front is being discussed at every levels.

Students involvements (DeYoung et al. (2016)) research has continued to show that one of the critical barriers to student's participation is the issue of student's involvements. When it comes to student's involvements, it calls for challenges since students are more less like volunteers and most of the time they have competitive compromises to make with time and studies. Balancing the two is often very difficult. As they make choices between what to do for personal gain compared to that for the common good of the institution and the others, it becomes

very difficult to operate on purely voluntarism basis (Khefacha & Belkacem 2014).

Besides, the tenure of office is mostly one year and as such there is basically little time for them to do an effective work. this is because as they try to settle down and learn the art of involvement and negotiation skills as well lobbying, it becomes too late to practice as their tenure of office would end just as they have settled in their job successfully. This cycle of unaccomplished business continues for ages.

B. Institutional Dynamics.

Further studies (Duram and Williams,2015) show that students have faced more resistance with institutions of higher learning in terms of bureaucracy and traditional mechanism of the way these institutions have been running for years. They have found it easier to modify individual behaviour than institutional changes. This study reveal further, that what brings more sparks in the institutions of higher learning is the fact the despite coming up with brilliant solutions that could affect positive changes to favour the students populous and the institution in general, the rigidity and the mechanical beauracatic tendencies often cause the aggressive conflict between students and management to intensify aggressively. This inertia has proved to be consistent and dynamic.

C. Funding Mechanisms

Another study that was conducted by Bratman et al (2016). shows that funding is yet another barrier that hinder effective student's participation in decision-making process. This study postulate that despite all the brilliant initiatives that could trigger change and improve the standards in the institutions of higher learning, lack of finances and the struggle for bare operational costs puts all the ideas of taking the processes to zero despite all the efforts invested into the productivity and viability of the systems. Universities now are turning out to begin to capitalise their processes for commercial benefits so as to survive. All universities are striving to go commercial as they term themselves to be business entities in order to generate their own income for a long term survival. They begin to see students as customers and their institutions as businesses which they can much to yield profits both in the short and long term basis.

D. Pre-Conditioned Perceptions

In yet another study (Staggenborg & Ramos, 2016) it has been discovered that one of the barriers to effective student's participation in decision making involves the limitation with regards to preconceived mindset of the managers towards students. A lot of higher authorities in the institutions of higher learning are not willing to talk or dialogue with students. They take students as trouble makers. This study conducted by Khefacha & Belkacem(2014) clearly shows that managers are a big obstacle to effective student's decision making process. An average student on the other hand is non-violent, cooperative and harmless. Once students are given the fare platform to be heard and to express themselves freely, they

can bring out the best that can add value to the health running of the institutions (Jones 2012).

IV. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study used qualitative methodological design in an explorative perspective. It used strategies of explore, describe and predict whereby all the respondents were required to share their views openly and freely. They brought out their opinions, experiences and values in order to understand the full meaning of the phenomenon under investigation. The study was a real situation problem looking for clear answers to the problem of student's participation. Therefore, a qualitative research design was more suitable as it aimed at exploring in details the nature of the problems and the possible solutions to it.

A. Sampling Methods and Data Collection

Both probabilistic and non-probabilistic sampling techniques were used to investigate the problem to the fullest. A sample size of 30 respondents were used which included 2 student's union leaders (purposely selected), 2 Dean of students Affairs officers (purposely selected), and 26 students randomly selected using simple random sampling techniques. Data was collected using semi-structured questionnaires and focused group discussions.

B. Data Analysis And Interpretations

The data was analysed using thematic analysis methods whose findings was presented using themes.

V. THE RESEARCH FINDINGS

The outline below shows the summaries of the findings of the study as obtained from the primary research data. The main aim of the study was to explore what constituted student's participation using the lenses of students. The current student's Union structures with several representations on the university governance structures proposes and suggests that there was enough student's representation on the university governance structures in the daily making of the decisions in the life of institutions of higher learning. Contrary to this assertions, the study clearly indicated that what currently appear to be student's full representation does not anywhere come close to it. The highlight of the findings has been shared below.

A. Current Union Structures Representative of Students

The major findings of the study showed that the majority of the students did not believe that the structure of the union fully represented the majority students populous. When students were asked to indicate whether they believed that the students union offered full representation, the majority strongly disagreed to that assertion. They cited that there was really a clear gap between student's majority and their union leadership. The few students in leadership often seemed to be closer to management than to their fellow students. This is why one of the respondents indicated that in most cases while the union leaders were still discussing in meetings, there would be a riot or protest already in action.

B. Confidence in the Student's Unions

The majority of the students interviewed further disclosed that they had no confidence in the union leadership as the majority interest of the students populous were never taken into account by their leaders. More and more students claimed that student's leaders favoured management views on any particular matter and ignored student's interests despite them being voted into office by students.

C. Influence of the Union on the University Governance Structures

Due the skewed numbers of students who sat on the board and other university governance structures, it was perceived that their numbers and the ratios of representations highly favoured management and disadvantaged the student's interests. In this regards, students felt the representation in reality does not exist owing to their low numerical representation on the board and their poor bargaining skills that existed in the meeting where students were called to represent their fellow students. When you look at the ratio of student's representatives versus the numbers of the population of students they represented compared with sizes of the management against the small population of staff they represented, even simple logic could not come in term with that reality. Besides, there were lack of informal governance structures to accord the majority of students' opportunities to participate in decision making processes fairly and equitably.

Additionally, students' leadership lacked negotiation skills, leadership skills and there was no orientation given to them on how the formal university governance structures function in relations to the process of decision making process.

D. Proposed Union Structures

When students were interviewed further as to what structures would be proposed to be more representative and skewed to student's interests, the majority suggested that there was need to come up with a structure that had local governance characteristics with devolutionary tendencies where decisions were to be made at the lowest levels where the majority of students existed rather than those lean and centralised formal institutional governance structures. They further mentioned that what worked in Europe may not work in Africa. Further they accented to the fact that the local unions structures must be fully localised to the African set up of doing business rather than those system of structures that were more Eurocentric in nature and pro-management in styles.

E. Benefits of Student's Participations

The study further indicated that there were so much benefits to student's participation in decision-making process and the majority of the benefits included the fact that students' participation led to grooming of future leadership. It also can be mentioned that student's participation often led to peaceful environment of studies as students could less likely riot or exhibit antisocial

behaviours. Students participation was also cited as the major prerequisite for knowledge sharing, problem solving and the avenue for creating student's ownership to project that required full support of the majority students populous for success and effective implementations.

VI. DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

A. Introductions

This section will discuss the main finding of the research. The study focuses on an Ecological perspective of decolonising student's participatory systems of decision making process in institutions of higher learning in relation to antisocial behaviour: An auto photographic student Perspective. It is observed that the current union formal organisation structures do not inspire much confidence in the promotion of the majority student's participation in decision making process. Since the current structures on the student's guild are perceived to ride on the colonial predesigned organisation systems of governances whose relevance to the local and indigenous tastes may leave much to be desires in terms of the effectiveness in securing maximum platforms for student's majority participation in decision making process, a lot of questions have been raised.

Research shows that the more the levels of student's participatory rate in the systems of the decisions making process the more the health inter-relationships between student's bodies and management (Jones 2012). It is further expected that the institutions of higher learning will record stability, harmony and create a peaceful learning environment that promote academic excellence hence leading to securing equity and quality in the management of institutions of higher learning.

B. Current Union Structures Representative of Students

With the current student's guild structures that comes with the legislature, judiciary and executive the majority of students perceive that this system promotes an elite society of ministers that are completely isolated from the majority of students populous. With this formal governance structures it was observed that, it lacked informal structures that promotes the majority students participatory rule systems as it is too formal and isolates itself from the environment where the majority of students exist. The majority of students felt that in order to help bridge this gap, there was need to introduce more informal and semi-formal structures with characteristics of local systems of governance structures that promote devolution of power and decentralization of decision making process to allow the majority of students and create a rich platform for participation, dialogue and engagements. This will ensure that a link is firmly created between the union leadership and the majority of the student's movements in the student's governance systems. This perspective view is line with the findings of Carey(2013) who argued that devolution of power increases participation in the governance structure as it aims to solicit majority participation in formal decision making process.

The devolution of powers will further create more informal platform structures where the majority of students will feel part of the central decision making process and this will in turn improve student's participation in decision making process. Some of the informal structures for instance will ensure that at the local hostels levels, all students will easily participate in decision making process thereby help in enhancing to create harmony, transparency and accountability in the operations of the student's affairs in the university. Furthermore, the devolutionary systems will eventually create a strong link between the majority of the students and university management. Once the link is in place, there will be more positive students behaviour that works against students antisocial behavioural tendencies and there will be more harmony, peace and tranquillity that promote excellence and quality in political, academic and social achievements.

C. Confidence in the Student's Unions

The main findings of this study indicated that the majority of students populous lacked confidence in student's unions and this development normally contributes to low levels of student's participation in decision making. Generally, the majority of students often feel the union leaders affiliate more with management as opposed to the majority students interest more especially that there are the ones who voted them into office. A closer inquiry into this matter further revealed that in most instances the majority student's interests are often ignored in preferences to managements interests even when their demands might be in the best interest of the institution and this often leads to loss of confidence in union leadership. Numerous studies (stellabosnch 2018; Petersen 2011) have also shown that the majority of students do not have confidence in students union leadership due their incapability to effectively handle students matters that are in the best interest of the majority students. However, more recent studied have further shown that this lack of confidence sometimes emanates from the fact that the majority of students in leadership lack preliminary trainings, orientations and practical knowledge in effective leadership skills, negotiation abilities, advocacy and general managerial competencies. This often make them important when it comes to their representation of students matters to management even at higher levels of institutional governance structures where they represent their fellow students. In view of this solid reality, it is therefore recommended that once students are elected to student leadership positions, there is need to train them in soft skills such as general management, leadership, decision making and negotiation skills. This will make them perform better and improve their qualities of student's representations.

D. Influence of the Union on the University Governance Structures

There are several factors that influence student's effectiveness in the general representation of their fellow students in decision making process. Some of these include, the personal competencies, numbers of representations, the attitudes of the university management towards students, supports and courage as well the environment or platform where the discussion take place. The study disclosed that

there was poor influence from the union leadership when it comes to student's effective representation in formal university governance structures. It has been observed that in most cases the main factors that precipitated the low influence of the students on the university decision making process had mainly to do with poor relevant skills of students' leaders, negative staff students perception and the imbalances of representation of the students numbers on the university governance structures. This study is in tandem with the popular arguments raised by many classic scholars (Gerom et al 2020, Lukas 2017, Jerom 2011) that have clearly indicated that poor skills in leadership, negotiations skills and decision making skills have often compromised the quality of students' representations in decision making process. Students leadership might come with great ideas to the discussion table with good intentions. However, lack of leadership skills and basic negotiations skills affect the leadership ability to effectively represent their electorates in higher decision making bodies of the university governance structures.

Sometimes however, it was about the negative perceptions that senior university management team might have towards the student's unionism. Many studies have shown that what impedes the quality of dialogue might be the ill-preconceived nature of the senior university administrators against students and this tends to create a hostile platform that often compromises the quality of dialogue and engagements between union leaders and management. What must be clearly is that unions are a legal mandate in line with the Zambia constitution. Unions are necessary in the university governance regardless of who is charge at any specific time. For the higher institution of learning to operate effectively, they need student's union. Management and union must operate symbiotically with mutual respect and tenacity both in the short and long terms basis.

In view of this theoretical understanding, there is need for management staff to always develop a positive opinion towards the existence of the students in institutions of higher learning. There must be also efforts towards the improvements of work relations between students and unions in a consistent and continuous manner. Additionally, the environment of the discussion meetings must be levelled in terms of equity, balanced discussion and consultative manner. It is not encouraged to create an aggressive dialogue environment while expecting quality of delivery of service. This might not be possible especially that students are traditionally perceived to give respect to adults in any setup of the community and as such once the discussion table in not conducive, it is impossible to achieve equity in decision making process.

E. Proposed New Governance Students' Union Structures

The current students' union structure has been observed to sustain colonial weaknesses through its mechanical systems that creates an elite class that is divorced from the majority students populous thereby leading to a wide participatory gap between students and its leadership and also between students' leadership and the

university management. The student's union structure is typically a western styles prototype whose applicability to the Zambian environment comes with a lot of doubts. Currently, there are three arms of governance structures when it comes to student's union leadership structure. There is executive that includes the cabinet which is in charge of the daily running of the union for the purposes of planning and administration. The legislature, SRC, is in charge of making laws and policies while the judiciary is in charge of interpretation of the laws.

The study findings have recommended for decentralisation of decision making process that come with devolution of power from the centre to the local formal and informal structure of decision making process. The majority of students currently do not participate in decision making process due to the non-availability of adequate structures that promote governance at local grassroots levels. Students have high interest to participate in decision making processes. However, what is lacking are the defined formal and informal local governance structures that bring decision-making processes closer to the majority students populations for enhanced participation and representation.

The proposed structure of new student's representations aims at creation of wards and community development platform where all the ideas of funding and projects can begin from the lowest levels and from each ward some representatives can proceed to appear in the full council chambers to convey the message from the majority students populous in a systematic and organised manner. The system of local governance in practice have proved to be the most effect way of managing people in any set of mobilization because the ordinary people are empowered with responsibilities of planning, decision making and implementation of programs.

This system does not only enhance the levels of majority participation, it also builds capacity, leadership skills, experiences, accountabilities and transparency in the administration of student's business. Research also supports that local governance structures are the most effective way to enhance, strengthen and support a sustainable majority representation from the lowest levels in student's management in the institutions of higher learning. We need to create both formal and informal platforms that bring the majority of students together for dialogue and discussion towards solving student's problems in the most effective and efficient manners.

F. A Model that Enhances Student’s Participation in Decision Making Process in HEI

Fig 1 A Model that Enhances Student’s Participation in Decision Making Process in HEI
 Source: Field data -A model of student’s participatory framework with local governance participatory structures.

In fig 1, it can be observed that the proposed model enhances majority students’ participation in decision making process. It creates both formal and informal platforms for the purposes of creating extra platforms and opportunities to allow as many students as possible to take part in the governance of the institution of higher learning. This typological design comes as a proposed solution to the weaknesses that have been sustained in the current student’s guild. The student’s guild is too formal and highly centralised. It creates an elite minority class of the ruling class that comprises the ministers in different portfolios that are completely detached from the majority of the students.

The proposed structures however suggest of a decentralised system of governance structures that bring the students majority closer to the governance structures. Power and resources are brought closer to the common students who otherwise could not have any chance of participating in any governance structures.

Once this model is adopted and implemented, it shall increase students’ participation in decision making process leading to a healthy and more motivated environment of learning where students and management can interact and fully collaborate in decision making towards a more collegial and strategic institutional of higher learning.

G. Benefits of Students' Participation

There are numerous benefits that comes with increased student's participation in decision making process. Research shows that increased students participation in the governance issues tend to bring a change of behavioural patterns in the students' movements that work against antisocial students behaviours, improved socialisations, harmony, transparency, accountabilities and transparency. When the majority of students are actively participating, it creates a health university environment of continuous dialogue and collaborations that target at elimination of students antisocial behavioural tendencies. It brings about good values of excellent leadership qualities, discipline, academic freedom and joint ventures between management and students groups.

Participations further tend to encourage ownership of programs implementation for the students' communal developmental projects. Once students feel that they are part and parcel of the decision making process, they tend to support the projects and program implementation and this in turn leads to success in project actualisation, monitoring and evaluation. The tendencies to sabotages and theft and cheating are drastically reduced. Students themselves form a formidable pool of security to support the program implementation that management is embarking upon.

Further, student's participation and representation helps eliminate the communication barriers that happened between policy initiative and implementation. There is always serious information gap that exist between management and student's movement which sometimes could be the sources of tension and conflict in the university. Once there is a conduisive collaborative initiative, students are brought closer to the forefront of decision making platform and there is enhanced communication between the managers and the students majority in general.

VII. RECOMMENDATIONS

This study is very important to the effective management of student's affairs on campus. It attempts to establish the current existing flaws that impedes the actualisation of student's participation in the process of decision making process. In order to provide effective administration of student's governance systems, we need to appreciate how best we can enhance collaborations of student's leadership with respect to management in higher institutions of learning. In view of the above it is recommended that the following be considered: -

- *There is need to restructure the student's leadership governance structures in order to increase students' participation. These structures must come with local governance decentralisations patterns that advocate for devolution of power.*
- *In order for the student's leaders to perform well, we need to provide soft skills training in leadership, management, problem solving and negotiation skills.*

- *There is need to also orient management staff of the university on the student's dynamics and student's governances so as to keep a positive image of students*
- *There is need to create more informal platforms in order to increase students' participation in governance structures*
- *Management must also offer support to the students' union in order to motivate them in their roles.*

VIII. CONCLUSION

Contrary to the popular view that student's unions offer participations of students in decision making process in the general governance of student's affairs, the research indicated that participation from the student's view point is very different. The majority of students perceived that the current colonial structures of student's governance lack platforms that promote the majority of student's participation in decision making process. It is therefore recommended that local government governance structures be introduced in order to solicit maximum students' collaborations. The more students are able to participate in the governance structures using more informal provisionary structures the more it lead to positive students behavioural patterns, This creates more harmony, confidence, build more healthy leadership relationships between student's and management, Students are less likely to protest or resolve to exhibit antisocial behaviours due to the smooths environment that is provided for through increased levels of students participation in decisions making process.

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